

GINAMO workshop on genetic diversity indicators in Belgium

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REPORT

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GINAMO Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring

Genetic diversity is the foundation of biodiversity and essential for the long-term survival, adaptation, and resilience of populations, species, and entire ecosystems. While genetic diversity has long been neglected in biodiversity policy and management, the current Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) includes a strong goal and target for genetic diversity conservation and also monitoring, including with indicators and for wild species. Tools and indicators to assess and monitor genetic diversity are available but are rarely applied due to the gap in knowledge transfer between conservation science and application. GINAMO is a project of Biodiversa+, The European Biodiversity Partnership, which assesses and delivers science-based and co-designed best practices and guidelines for the use of genetic diversity indicators. This will enable the routine integration of genetic criteria and indicators into biodiversity monitoring and assessments, from policy at regional, national, and EU levels, to global conventions and obligations. A key component of GINAMO is the use of facilitated group decision-making processes to partner and co-decide from the outset with the stakeholder community. This ensures that all resources produced meet their concerns, reporting duties, and monitoring needs, and that guidelines and work flows are more likely to be adopted. Easy-to-apply, standardised and automated workflows will be co-created for assessing genetic indicators to meet national reporting obligations and to incorporate genetic diversity knowledge into nature management plans.

Main objectives

GINAMO uses existing open access genetic and non-genetic data (including Earth observation data) to best determine accurate estimates of the two genetic diversity indicators of the GBF: 1) the proportion of populations within species with an effective population size (N_e) greater than 500 ($N_e > 500$ hereafter), and 2) the proportion of populations maintained within species. To maximise the implementation and reporting of these indicators, GINAMO designs, facilitates, and scientifically evaluates co-creation processes between scientists and country stakeholders in France, Italy, Norway, Sweden and Belgium. These processes aim to collaboratively develop workflows that are scientifically sound, appropriate, compliant with policy and easy-to-implement for nature management.

Main activities

GINAMO focuses on generating best practices for assessing effective population size and evaluating genetic indicators from both DNA-based data and non-DNA (proxy) data from multiple sources. Additionally, GINAMO evaluates how satellite Earth observation data can be used to generate proxies to monitor genetic diversity. Workflows for existing and newly generated information will be standardised to provide easily accessible tools for researchers, nature managers and policy makers. GINAMO activities follow a co-creation approach under professional guidance by the European Regional Resource Center of the IUCN SSC [Conservation Planning Specialist Group](#) and with scientific evaluation by social scientists, so that methods and products are produced together by policy makers, nature managers, and scientists.

Workshop process

The workshops organised by GINAMO in collaboration with local country stakeholders serve to create input to the best practice guidelines that will be produced. In order to make these as user friendly and as relevant as possible, it is important to understand the realities in which various stakeholders operate, and to understand the challenges they experience from their perspective. The challenges identified during the workshops will inform the work of the various work packages within GINAMO, when developing the science and methods behind the use of genetic indicators.

IUCN SSC CPSG Europe designed and facilitated the country workshop processes, in line with CPSG's Principles and Steps (Appendix III), and informed by preparatory meetings with a country organising group composed of GINAMO scientists from the country and selected country stakeholders with a central role in monitoring and reporting on biodiversity.

In preparation of the workshops, a generic workflow was developed (Fig 1), that outlines the main steps that need to be taken within a country in order to be able to report genetic indicators to the CBD. This workflow was used as the basis for the discussions during the workshop.

Fig 1. The generic workflow used as a base for the workshop.

The agenda for the workshop can be found in Appendix I. Following an introduction to the GINAMO project and the genetic indicators, as well as to the workshop process and generic workflow, the active part of the workshop started. Participants first identified where in the workflow they felt their institution could have a role to play. Next, the generic workflow was divided into three parts:

1. Selection of the species to monitor and report on.
2. Data collection, indicator calculation, and storing and structuring of metadata for future reporting cycles.
3. Preparing the relevant parts of the CBD report

For each of these three parts, the participants:

- A. Discussed their knowledge of the current situation in Belgium
- B. Identified the challenges facing them as stakeholders, or the country as a whole, in order to end up with a fully functional, and repeatable workflow that can routinely and consistently produce genetic indicators for consecutive reporting cycles to CBD.

At the end of the workshop, the participants reviewed all the challenges and selected those for which they felt that developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country.

Participants

The country organising group identified the stakeholders that would be invited to the workshop. A matrix was developed to help identify stakeholders that represented a wide variety of workflow steps, skills, roles and responsibilities, as well as geographical placement, when relevant. Not all the identified stakeholders were able to participate in the workshop, but they will all receive this report.

12 stakeholders representing Belgium's three regions (the Flemish Region, the Brussels-Capital Region, and the Walloon Region) and various research institutions and NGO's participated. A short description of the institutions represented can be found in Appendix II.

Workshop evaluation

GINAMO's social scientists will evaluate the entire co-creation process. In order to evaluate the country workshops, a survey was prepared and completed by all participants before and after the workshop. The only parts from that survey included in this report are any answers to the question: "List any stakeholders who could have made a valuable contribution but were not present at this workshop". The overall results from this evaluation will be shared at a later stage.

Workshop results

Workshop outcomes

1. An overview of the current situation in Belgium with regards to: genetic monitoring and reporting, genetic and proxy data gathering and databases, already existing workflows, important stakeholder groups, scientific views regarding the use of the *Ne 500* headline indicator, etc.
2. A list of challenges facing the stakeholders and the country to have a fully functional workflow that is repeatable for consecutive reporting cycles for the CBD.

3. A selection of those challenges for which developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country.

This report collects the results from the workshop in Belgium, and reflects the thoughts, assumptions and knowledge of the participants at the time of the workshop, but does not claim to give the full picture of the status and challenges with regards to the reporting of genetic indicators to the CBD in Belgium. The aim of this report is to inform further work by GINAMO and hopefully it will also prove to be a useful first step towards further work and collaboration within Belgium, to develop and implement a national workflow.

Where in the workflow stakeholders' institutions might contribute

The workshop participants identified where in the workflow they felt their institution might have a role to play. The results are in the table below. Please note that this does not constitute an exhaustive list of stakeholders required for each workflow step.

Data on species is generated	Data about species is stored	Species list to monitor and report on	Data is collected, structured and stored	Indicators are calculated and stored	The report to the CBD is written and submitted
DEMNA	INBO	INBO	INBO	INBO	ANB
Natuurpunt/ Beheer	DEMNA	DEMNA	DEMNA	DEMNA	INBO
KMDA-CRC	Brussels Environment	Brussels Environment	Brussels Environment	Brussels Environment	
INBO	Natuurpunt	Natuurpunt			
		ANB			

The following organisations were identified as missing from the workshop:

- Belgian Biodiversity Platform
- CUZ
- DNF
- FOD ([Federal Public Service of Belgium)
- Natagora
- Researchers at specific university (working around biodiversity)
- Royal Belgian Institute for Natural Sciences (KBIN-IRSNB)
- VLIZ

Summary of current situation in Belgium

Belgium has three major regions, Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels with regional agencies (INBO, SPW/DEMNA and Brussels Environment) who are responsible for monitoring and reporting on international commitments for their region.

There have not yet been collaborations between regions to discuss and determine species to monitor and report the genetic indicators to the CBD..

INBO has the mandate and the budget to choose species and do the work autonomously,for Flanders while the SPW/DEMNA is smaller with fewer resources.

INBO participated in a study where the genetic indicators for ca. 900 species in 9 countries were calculated using proxy data. However, the chosen species were not based on a national strategic methodology but on species for which data was easily available.

The [NBSAP \(National Biodiversity Strategy Plan\) for Belgium](#) mentions genetic diversity but no genetic indicators. It does mention (p.42) that biodiversity indicators should be streamlined among regions. There is also no currently accepted national list of species for which Belgium will monitor and calculate genetic indicators for the CBD report which is due in February 2026. Nor were the participants in the workshops aware of what the report will look like. Normally, for international reports, the regions write their own chapter for a report, and these are simply combined in the final report.

Challenges

The workflow for reporting to CBD was divided into three parts, and for each part, the workshop participants identified a list of challenges facing the stakeholders and the country to have a fully functional workflow that is repeatable for consecutive reporting cycles for the CBD.

After identifying the challenges, the participants reviewed them all and selected those for which they felt that developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country. It was possible to mark a challenge as both a co-creation candidate and as a challenge that needs national work to be solved -

but that is not indicated in this report. The challenges marked with (G) are the ones that were suggested for co-creation.

Species list to monitor and report on (and associated data generation challenges)

1. Design the species selection process for Belgium, centered around monitoring of species that are good indicators of ecosystem health. (G)
 - a. Agree on how many and which greater ecosystems in Belgium
 - i. Set/check criteria for each ecosystem separately
 - b. Agree on how many and which indicator species to select per ecosystem (taking feasibility into account)
 - i. Identify the experts that can identify good indicator species (the collective of the workshop participants knows who to ask)
 - ii. Which species are particularly good to use as indicators for ecosystem health?
 - c. Online process for the above ecosystem and species selection work
2. Gather and coordinate the experts to develop the species list (coordinating team or person). (G)
3. Limited resources - both in time, personnel and financial costs is an issue.
4. Find out if there is a need for an official approval for the list (may differ in the regions)?
5. How do we deal with species that are hunted and thus managed?
6. Should we include species that other (e.g. neighbouring) countries also monitor to be able to compare - which species would be relevant? (G)
7. How can citizen science data contribute, and does it include enough data to be able to use it for calculating genetic indicators?
8. Reduce biases in observational data (not uniformly distributed).

Data is collected, structured and stored and the indicators are calculated

1. How do we ensure that everybody doing the calculations has adequate training so that the methodology is used correctly and consistently? (G)
2. How do you deal with species where biological data is missing for certain regions in the country?
3. Understand the KOBO form approach and assess if it is appropriate to be used in Belgium, or if there is a need for something else in Belgium. (G)
4. Identify where and how to store metadata, plus the KOBO form (or equivalent tool)? (G)
5. Aggregate data sources (currently required data may be spread over different databases) and ensure access for those involved in data collection and calculation.
6. Identify what approach to take for each species - how is population defined, what are the assumptions made etc. (G)
7. Does it matter that the indicators are calculated with different methods for the various species?
8. How do you deal with expanding species and with species whose populations are increased due to fragmentation?

The report to the CBD is written and submitted

1. Complete species selection by 2026 and decide whether to report on all or a selection of these for the first reporting of the genetic indicators in 2026.
2. Design and agree on a table structure (one table nationally) for reporting the genetic indicators in the report; and identify someone to coordinate gathering the indicator values.
3. Write a section that explains the methodology for selecting species and calculating indicators. (G)
4. Should reporting genetic indicators be a separate system or should it be integrated in other schemes?
5. Who takes the lead and manages this process for the whole country?

Conclusions by the stakeholders

There is a clear wish to collaborate more across regions for reporting genetic indicators, to avoid double work but also to ensure that the work being done will have the largest impact on policy and management.

There is consensus around a general methodology for selection of species for long term genetic monitoring, namely to focus on species that are good indicator species for Belgium's greater ecosystems. The first step would be to gain agreement on how many and which ecosystems to focus on and then, in consultation with the relevant experts, to identify the species that best reflect ecosystem health. That way the genetic indicators could be used to monitor the genetic diversity of the species, but also the larger health of the ecosystem.

There also seemed to be consensus on aspiring integration with existing monitoring and reporting, such as the EU birds- and habitats directive, to guide species selection for genetic monitoring.

The aim for the participating parties is to create a consolidated "Belgian" species list by the end of 2026 and to then decide whether to report on all of these, or to limit the first report in 2026 to a smaller number of species, for example those with data/GI's already available.

There was consensus concerning how data should be presented in the CBD report in 2026. The proposal is to prepare a simple, short report, presenting the indicator values in a commonly designed table with a short text explaining the methodology.

To be determined later, is whether to also prepare a separate, more elaborately written and beautifully presented report, with the aim to drive action and policy decisions..

The differences in the INBOs and SWP/DEMNA's structure and mode of operating will need to be considered moving forward.

Next steps

The GINAMO work packages will assess all challenges selected by the five countries as potentially benefiting from collaboration between GINAMO and the country stakeholders. The GINAMO work package members will assess if and how these can be incorporated into their work, and how the country stakeholders might be able to contribute. The result of this will then be reported back to the country workshop participants, together with potential next steps.

Reference materials

- Belgium has committed to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and must report to the CBD using novel genetic indicators for the first time, among a large range of indicators, first in February 2026, and then periodically, typically every three to four years. Critical steps are the selection of species to report on, collecting and interpreting available data on them for the calculation of indicators, and using a reproducible approach to building successive reports. Guidelines for these steps are available:
 - CBD guidelines:
<https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/92cf/b458/18519b4c0b487bf9bfc23988/sbstta-26-inf-14-en.pdf>
 - Guidelines from the Coalition of Conservation Genetics:
<https://ccgenetics.github.io/guidelines-genetic-diversity-indicators/>
 - <https://doi.org/10.17161/bi.v18i.22332>
- Genetic diversity must be protected because it allows for the long-term persistence, resilience and adaptive potential of species.
 - policy brief: <https://g-bikegenetics.eu/en/multimedia-policy-briefs-pubs/policy-briefs>
- The genetic indicators are pragmatic and can be computed using DNA data or non-DNA proxy data.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae006>
 - <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-024-01632-8>
- These indicators have been tested and validated for use in 9 countries, including Belgium.
 - <https://doi.org/10.32942/X2WK6T>
- National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) can be improved to include the protection of genetic diversity.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae106>

APPENDIX I: Workshop Agenda

AGENDA - Belgium

09.00	Welcome / Introduction / Survey1	12.30	LUNCH
09.40	Presentation on GINAMO and genetic indicators	13.30	CS/C: Data extraction and calculation of indicators
10.15	BREAK	14.30	CS/C : reporting to Convention on Biological Diversity (CDB))
10.30	Workshop process/ reporting workflow	15.15	PAUSE
10.45	Participant introductions / organisational involvement	15.30	Sorting of challenges
11.15	Current Situation and Challenges (CS/C): species list	16.15	Next steps/Closure/Survey2
		17.00	THE END

Photo: Carina Lundmark, GINAMO

APPENDIX II: List of institutions represented

INBO

INBO is the independent research institute of the Flemish government that supports and evaluates biodiversity policy and management through applied scientific research, data and knowledge disclosure.

Natuurpunt

Natuurpunt is an independent volunteer organization that ensures the protection of vulnerable and endangered nature in Flanders.

Brussels Environment

Brussels Environment is the environmental administration of the Brussels-Capital Region. This government body deals with environmental protection, nature conservation, waste and energy management, air quality, noise pollution control, and climate policy in Brussels. It develops and enforces environmental regulations, promotes sustainable practices, and raises awareness among citizens to ensure a healthy living environment in the capital.

Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences

The Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences is a scientific institution in Brussels dedicated to natural research, biodiversity study, and the management of natural history collections. The institute conducts scientific research on ecosystems, evolution, and palaeontology, provides scientific advice to governments, and manages an extensive natural history museum including the famous collection of dinosaur skeletons. In addition, it provides educational programs, monitors Belgian biodiversity, and participates in international scientific research and nature conservation initiatives.

SPW/DEMNA

SPW/DEMNA stands for Public Service of Wallonia/Department of Natural and Agricultural Environment Studies. This institution functions as the scientific research center of the Walloon government for nature management and agriculture. DEMNA collects and analyzes data on biodiversity, ecosystems, and agricultural practices in Wallonia, monitors natural habitats, conducts scientific studies to support environmental policy, manages natural databases, and provides expertise for nature conservation and sustainable agriculture in the Walloon region.

ANB (Agency for Nature and Forest), Brussels

ANB aims to work towards more and better forests, and more and better nature and green spaces. ANB invests in a contemporary policy and management of forests, nature, and parks and supports partners who pursue the same goals.

Royal Zoological Society of Antwerp

Royal Zoological Society of Antwerp (KMDA) hosts a research institute, the Antwerp ZOO Centre for Research and Conservation (CRC) which uses applied and basic research in zoos and field stations, in laboratories, and at universities globally to inform practical zoo husbandry and management and species conservation.

APPENDIX III: IUCN SSC CPSG

Our **mission**: to save threatened species by increasing the effectiveness of conservation efforts worldwide

Our **mantra**: every species that needs a plan is covered by an effective and implemented plan

For over 40 years we've accomplished this by:

- Providing culturally sensitive and respectful facilitation for stakeholder-inclusive conservation action planning.
- Developing and sharing innovative, interdisciplinary science-based tools and methods.
- Building capacity for species conservation planning worldwide.